

Women Empowerment and its Effects on Household Food Security in Kalagala Sub County of Luweero in Uganda

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Abstract

The study tends to ask why despite the fact that women have been exposed to various training programs in Kalagala there is still food shortage in terms of quality and quantity among households is thus portending food security issue in Uganda. The researchers objectivised the study through; examination of the empowerment women and its effect on household food security in Kalagala sub county of Luweero in Uganda and finding out whether the empowerment women receive equips them with skills and knowledge to maintain household food security in Kalagala sub-county of Luweero. Additionally, through conceptualization, the researcher was viewing at Women Empowerment and its effect on household food security and expected (though not hypothesized) that if women are empowered, they should have financial abilities and skills enhancement, and knowledge to help them acquire resources like land they can access credit which will help them in maintaining household food security. The study employed descriptive research design with both qualitative and quantitative methods of analysis being conducted in Kalagala sub-county of Luweero district, found in central Uganda. A sample size was 380 households drawn from Yamane (1967) formula. The researchers used both questionnaires and interviews to collect data. Data analysis of data was done both quantitatively and qualitatively. In its recommendation, Women's Empowerment should be viewed from the perspectives of the underlying principles. This therefore means empowering women is to enable them participate fully in economic life across available sectors as an essential to building stronger economies both locally and internationally to achieve the global goals from MDGs to SDGs.

Keywords: Women Empowerment/ Empowered Women/ Food Security Effects/Food Security/ Household Food Security/ Kalagala/ Luweero/ Uganda.

Introduction and Background to the Study

The right to food is a fundamental human right. Yet millions of people suffer the “ravages of hunger and malnutrition or the consequences of food insecurity”. Food security is fundamental to individual human dignity, growth and survival (<http://www.usda.gov> 1999). Regardless of the level of development achieved by the respective economies, women play a crucial role in agriculture and in rural development in most countries of the world. Therefore, empowering women who play the most important role as producers of food is key to achieving food security. This study on Women Empowerment and its effect on household food security were carried out in Kalagala sub-county of Luweero district in Uganda.

Food, which is as old as mankind, affects every organism and is the foundation of every economy. Consequently, food security has been a target of every nation as well as individual households in the world for a long time.

FAO(2002) defines food security as “a situation that exists when all people at all times have physical, social and economic access to sufficient , safe and nutritious food that meets their dietary needs and food preferences for active and healthy life”. Accordingly, household food security is a condition arrived at when individual members of a specific family have either material, or financial access to sufficient, safe, and nutritious food stuffs to meet the dietary basic needs, at family level.

The concept of food security has gone through various transformations over the last several decades as the development theory in general. As early as 1948, the universal Declaration of Human Rights recognized the right to food as a core element of an adequate standard of living (Amanda 1999). The 1960s known as the ‘development decade’ was a time of hope for the third world which included the real aspiration of ending hunger. Until the 1980s the concept of food security was based on absolute food availability (WFD 2001).In

the 1980-1990s the paradigm shifted as policy began to explore individual and household food security as opposed to food security from a national perspective (Amanda 1999).

Women's role in agricultural production, throughout the developing world, was first empirically documented in the 1970's by Ester Boserup (Recka M 1997). Her work fostered the ideas behind the 'women in development' debate, which highlighted the inequality between men and women across societies and began to view women as untapped resources. According to <http://ideas.repec.org/p/wbk/wbrsp/232.htm> women play a key role in producing and providing food for the family, managing and allocating household resources and caring for children. In a study conducted in 2002 on household food security in Uganda, Bahiigwa (2002) identified women as key to household food security. He also noted that women have the primary responsibility for child care and food production while contributing to cash crop agriculture. FAO (2008) also affirms that people's access to food is dependent on the work of rural women. This is so because women farmers produce the majority of food. They are also responsible for ensuring that their family basic needs are met. (FAO 2008) estimates that women produce over 50% of all food grown worldwide.

In sub-Saharan Africa, women grow 80-90 percent of the food. Accordingly in sub Sahara Africa when women obtain the same levels of education, experience and farm inputs currently available to male farmers, they increase their yields by 22 % (Quisumbing and Meinzen-Dick (2001). Moreover women in sub-Sahara Africa and the near East play a major role in household animal production, enterprise. In all types of animal production systems women have a predominant role in processing particularly milk products and are commonly_ responsible for their marketing (FAO 2008). While both men and women are income earners and agricultural producers, women also process and prepare food, and use their income for their children's benefit (Thomas in Haddad, Hoddinott, and Alderman 1997; Carr 1991). Women also provide the majority of care for their families, take their children to health services, and ensure a healthy environment—the very components of good nutrition (Levin et al. 1999).

In a research conducted by Nanono in 2008 on the status and causes of Malnutrition, 27% children under five years are stunted, 25% are underweight and 19% are affected by acute malnutrition because of food insecurity in the area. This shows that despite the fact that women have received a lot of training in the area of food production, there is still a lot of food insecurity in the country. This research therefore focused on women emancipation and its effect on household food security in Kalagala Sub County of Luweero district in Uganda.

Problem Statement

Despite the fact that women have been exposed to various training programs especially those concerned with improving food security, there is still food shortage in terms of quality and quantity among households in Uganda (Bahiiigwa 2002). In Kalagala sub-county, People suffer absolute poverty and children suffer from malnutrition and the accompanying diseases like kwashiorkor, marasmus and rickets. They are also stunted due to inadequate intake of nutrients (Nanono 2008). However no study has been done on women Empowerment and its effect on household food security, more especially in Kalagala Sub county of Luweero and this call for a research.

Objective of the Study

The objectives guiding this study were;

- i. To examine the empowerment women and its effect on household food security in Kalagala sub county of Luweero in Uganda.
- ii. To find out whether the empowerment women receive equips them with skills and knowledge to maintain household food security in Kalagala sub-county of Luweero.

METHODOLOGY

The study employed descriptive research design with both qualitative and quantitative methods of analysis being conducted in Kalagala sub-county of Luwero district, found in central Uganda. A sample size was 380 households drawn from Yamane (1967) formula. The researchers used both questionnaires and interviews to collect data. Data analysis of data was done both quantitatively and qualitatively.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1: Conceptual framework

In this regard to conceptualization, the researcher was looking at Women Empowerment and its effect on household food security. It was expected that if women are empowered, they should have financial and skills enhancement, and knowledge to help them acquire resources like land they can access credit which will help them in maintaining household food security. If women are empowered, their attitude will be changed towards agricultural production hence food security. The study also focused on the mechanism empowered women put in place to combat household food insecurity.

RELATED LITERATURE

The Concept and Nature of Food Security

Food security is a comparatively recent term that refers to the sustained supply of appropriate food to everyone in a community to enable their healthy development. Over time, this concept has been operationally defined in a number of ways. Interest in this subject has broadened, specifically in relation to changes in the extent and nature of food problems worldwide. The 1974 United Nations World Food Summit (UNWFS) offered the first formal definition of food security, which focused on adequate production of food at the global and national levels. The Summit deduced that food security is the 'availability at all times of adequate world food supplies of basic foodstuffs to sustain a steady expansion of food consumption and to offset fluctuations in production and prices' (UN Report of the World Food Conference, 1974). In the 1996 Rome Declaration on World Food Security it was stated that 'Food security exists when all people at all times have physical and economic access to sufficient, safe and nutritious food that meets their dietary needs and food preferences for an active and healthy life'. The definitions include elements of availability (supplies of food), accessibility (both physical and economic), and utilization (physiological ability to absorb and utilize consumed nutrients) (USAID 1997). This is a contemporary definition that FAO reaffirmed in 2002 (Madeley 2002). Therefore, in accordance with Bonnard (2003), food security refers to when all people at all times have both physical and economical access to sufficient quantity, quality and variety foodstuffs to meet their culturally acceptable dietary needs for a productive and healthy life.

Upon revisiting the broader definition of food security, it evokes the essential elements of availability, accessibility, affordability and utilization. Consequently, food insecurity is no longer a mere failure of agricultural produce of adequate food at the national level, but also includes the failure of livelihoods to guarantee access to enough food at the household level. Food insecurity may also be viewed from macro and micro perspectives. The former refers to failures by large players such as governments and regional bodies, while the latter refers to the by failures households to meet food requirements for their members. We accept Maxwell's (2000) complex inter-linkages between the individual, the household, the community, the nation and the international community. Rosegrant et al. (2005) highlight this viewpoint when they state that 'household food security is a function of inter-related processes that happen at different geographic scales: international, national, regional/district, community, and intrahousehold'.

Correspondingly, household food security herein is a condition that prevails when individual members of a specific family have either material or financial access to sufficient, safe, and nutritious food stuffs to meet the dietary basic needs, at family level. It has three distinct variables: food availability measured by food production and food supply; food accessibility measured by the level of income; and food utilization measured by nutrition, health and care giving.

The right to food is an elementary human right. Food security is fundamental to individual human dignity, growth, and survival. We all pay for widespread hunger and malnutrition through sacrificed human potential, lost economic opportunity, social tension, violence, and war. Therefore, global food security is essential to world peace and national security' (US Action Plan 1999). The right to food is one of the most frequently preserved rights in international human rights law and is recurrently reaffirmed by governments (UN 1948, Butcher 1987, FAO and WHO 1993, FAO 1996, FAO 2002, FAO 2005, Diouf 2001, Diouf 2002 and IPCFS 2007). Yet, no human right has been so continuously and enormously violated in recent times as the right to food (Clover 2003, Diouf 2002). As a result, millions of people around the world suffer the consequences of food insecurity (Pontifical Council 1996, FAO 2010a). Restricted access to food and its limited availability is a serious threat to human life (Clover 2003). It is paradoxical that one of the most claimed essential of human rights, right to food, is the one disregarded most. The supply and availability of food has been a crucial factor shaping the emergence, development and persistence of human civilizations throughout the ages. Consequently, achieving food security is a major concern today for the global, African governments as well as households.

Food insecurity implies inaccessibility to sufficient food in terms of nutritional value, resulting in malnutrition. According to Smith 1997, Maxwell 1999, it is a serious global threat. According to the WHO (2006), 'Food insecurity, or the absence of food security, is a state that implies either hunger (due to problems with availability, access and use) or vulnerability to hunger in the future'. These elements are interrelated. The persistence of food insecurity threatens the stability of both the international and national community (FAO 1996). At the 2002 World Food Summit (WFS) the chairperson stated: 'Together with terrorism, hunger is one of the greatest problems the international community is facing' (WFS News 2002). Additionally, James Morris, Executive Director of the World Food Programme (WFP 2002), in his address to the UN Security Council in December 2002 about Africa's food insecurity, said: 'Never before has WFP had to contend with potential starvation of this magnitude on the African continent with the simultaneous outbreak of two enormous and complex crises exacerbated by HIV/AIDS and economic policy failures'.

Global Food Insecurity

Despite the fact that world food production has grown faster than world population in the recent past; worldwide the trends of food insecurity are alarming. A decade ago, more that 800 million people were deprived the most fundamental human right to food; they suffered from food insecurity, chronic hunger and malnutrition (UN Press Release 1998). Additionally, the same source approximates that more than 200 million, of those 800 million, were children. CARE (2009), on the other hand, insists that of the 1.3 billion people who live in absolute poverty around the globe, 70% are women. The progress in reducing food insecurity, especially in the developing world, has slowed and generally the number of undernourished people is actually growing.

According to FAO (2002; see also FAO 1999), it is estimated that some 840 million people were undernourished in 1998 to 2000: 11 million in the industrialised countries, 30 million in countries in transition and 799 million in the developing world. FAO (2002) further stated that 'at the beginning of the

new millennium, close to 800 million people in developing countries, (about 17% of their population), lack sufficient food to live healthy and active lives. The forecast for the future continues to be a cause for serious concern'. No continent or country has been spared by food insecurity. In the US, for instance, more than 38 million people were struggling to put food on the table as of 2006 (Learner 2006). Over 50 countries worldwide, mostly in Africa, do not produce enough food to feed their populations and cannot afford to purchase the necessary commodities (Save the Children 2002). The latest available data of those who do not have enough to eat have not changed much. The total number of those who suffer from chronic food insecurity in the world is estimated to have reached 1.023 billion in 2009 and is expected to decline by 9.6 percent to 925 million in 2010 (FAO 2010a; FAO 2010d).

The number of undernourished people had fallen by 40 million between 1990/92 and 1995/97 (FAO 1999). However, the average annual decrease of food insecurity has been only 2.5 million, far below the level required to reach the WFS goal (FAO 2002). Progress had to be accelerated to 24 million a year, almost ten times the current pace, in order to reach that goal. On the one hand, several factors are largely attributed to that decline. This includes the strong Global cereal harvests that improved access to food; the fall in international food prices since 2008; and increased economic growth foreseen in 2010 -especially in developing countries (FAO 2010a, CFS 2010, FAO 2010c and FAO 2010d). The IMF estimates that world economic output has increased by 4.2% in 2010, faster than previously expected, following a contraction of 0.6% in 2009 (IMF 2010). However, economic growth, while essential, will not be sufficient in itself to eliminate the problem of food insecurity within an acceptable period of time (FAO 2010a). The recent increase in food prices, if it persists, will create additional obstacles in improving food security (FAO 2010a).

The Committee on World Food Security (October 2010), observed that though the reduction of food insecurity is welcome, but it is still far from the reality with unacceptably high percentages and increasing structural hunger (CFS 2010). However, the number of those who are insecure is higher -925 million- in 2010 than expected (FAO 2010c, FAO 2010d).

Food Insecurity in African Countries

One of the most urgent and challenging issues facing the African continent is achieving food security for its people. Africa is badly affected by food insecurity. Famines are the most visible and extreme manifestation of acute food insecurity. Of the 39 countries worldwide that faced food emergencies at the beginning of 2003, 25 are found in Africa (Clover 2003). Asia-Pacific and sub-Saharan Africa accounted for 750 million of the hungry people in the world from 2003 to 2005. As a result of the global food crisis, an additional 41 million people in Asia-Pacific and another 24 million in sub-Saharan Africa have plummeted into food insecurity (FAO 2008; FAO/NGO 1996).

Africa, which reversed from being a key exporter of agricultural commodities into being a net importer (FAO/GIEWS 2002), has the highest percentage of undernourished people. Sub-Saharan Africa is home to almost a quarter of the developing world's hungry people. Almost half of her populations are highly vulnerable to food insecurity (FAO 1999). Specifically, over 50% of the populations of Ethiopia, Angola, Mozambique, Haiti, Somalia, and the Central African Republic suffer from chronic food insecurity (US Action Plan 2002). Acute food insecurity since 2003 is affecting 38 million people in Africa who are facing the outright risk of famine, with 24 000 dying daily due to food insecurity (Clover 2003). In agreement, Morris (2002; and WFP 2002) state: 'The reality is that right now 38 million people in Africa alone face an urgent and imminent threat to their peace, security and stability...' Subsequently, Africans receive the highest amount of emergency food aid, annually (Clover 2003). Aid officials estimated that their budget for Africa was US\$1.4 billion for feeding those who faced starvation for ending months of 2002 (Morris 2002). As of today, generally developing countries still account for 98% (925 million) of the world's undernourished people (FAO 2010a). Serious food shortages are also looming in several countries in the Horn of Africa where millions are without sufficient food. According to the former Nigerian President, Olusegun Obasanjo, Africa is far from achieving the first millennium goal (MDG) of reducing poverty and hunger by 2015 (The Tide Online, 2008).

Africa is also a region that has made the least progress towards food security (FAO 1999). The proportion of undernourished people is higher in Central, East and Southern Africa than in West Africa (FAO 1999). Comparatively, serious food insecurity afflicts fewer people elsewhere. With reference to specific examples,

according to FAO, South Africa faced the most severe food security crisis by 2003 (Gideon 2007), whereby 16.7 million people were food insecure (Clover 2003). Despite her own national 'food secure' status, 35% of her population, more than 14 million people, are estimated to be highly vulnerable to food insecurity and 43% of households suffer from food insecurity (Rose and Charlton 2002; Drimie and Lafon 2003; De Klerk et al., 2004). Additionally, according to Kenya Food Security Outlook (2010), almost six million of Kenya's 38 million inhabitants are food insecure; and they depend on some form of food aid. KFSO further states that: 'Food prices have remained over 100 percent higher than December average levels in most of the pastoral districts'.

The problem of food insecurity is indiscriminate. As of today, African nations still fall short of achieving the first MDG, despite the fact that their leaders have embraced MDGs by incorporating them into their national strategies. In most parts of Africa, achieving adequate food supplies for the whole year is increasingly becoming a tremendous challenge. As a result, at present, most Africans have not yet attained food security. Breman 2004, FAO 2008, rightly observed that 'food security is one of the most urgent issues facing Africa today'.

Food Insecurity in Uganda

Uganda is also Food insecure. Despite her fertile soil, favorable weather and a promising economy, Uganda is one of the poorest countries in the world. It experiences food insecurity both at national and household levels. Uganda has a relatively low national rate of food energy deficiency, rated at 37% (FEWS NET 1997) and at 36.8% (IFPRI 2006). Yet, majority of Ugandans do not have access to sufficient food (WEP 2006). The diet is poor consisting mainly of staple foods (roots and tubers) and rarely vegetables, fruits or animal proteins. WFP conducted a Comprehensive Food Security and Vulnerability Analysis (CFSVA) to gain a better understanding of households' food insecurity and vulnerability at the sub-national level. This CFSVA was done in collaboration with the Government of Uganda, UNICEF, the Institute of Public Health, the Faculty of Agricultural and Food Science of the University of Makerere, FEWS NET and the National Bureau of Statistics. In July-August 2005, it surveyed 2,987 households, covering 55 districts, excluding the urban district of Kampala. Their findings estimate that, nationally, about one million (5% of the total rural population) are food insecure with about 6.75 million people (31%) highly vulnerable to food insecurity and another 4 million (19%) moderately vulnerable (WEP 2006).

Food insecurity exists throughout the country but varies both geographically and amongst livelihood groups. Food insecurity is most highly concentrated in the north. According to WEP (2006), vulnerability and food insecurity are the highest in Gulu, Kitgum and Pader districts. About 357,000 people (33% of the population) are food insecure and about 411,000 people (38%) are highly vulnerable. In Apac and Lira districts, approximately 170,000 (12%) people are food insecure and 520,000 (37%) are vulnerable. In North-eastern Uganda, in Kotido, Moroto and Nakapiripirit districts of Karamoja, about 170,000 people (18%) are food insecure and about 430,000 people (46%) are vulnerable, totalling to 64%. Currently, high levels of food insecurity persist in Karamoja, approximately 37% of the population receiving food assistance to cover food deficits of 40-70% (FEWS NET 2010b). About 1.2 million people (53%) are vulnerable in the Kabermaido, Katakwi, Soroti, Kumi, Pallisa and Tororo districts. In South-western Uganda, in the districts of Kabale and Kisoro, about 407,000 people (60%) are highly vulnerable to food insecurity (WEP 2006).

Several factors have contributed to the forgoing condition. The Northern part of the country experienced brutal rebel activities for two decades, which caused loss of lives, internal displacement, and disruption of economic and social services. Socio-economic progress was challenged by prolonged rebellion in the north. Food insecurity in northern Uganda is primarily the result of: experienced conflict-induced instability; limited access to land for IDP and refugee households. This was in addition to continued attacks by the Lord's Resistance Army (LRA) which had prevented people from returning to their homes to cultivate their fields. There was also low productivity of land; poor market infrastructure; civil conflict; recurring droughts; high population growth; increasing poverty and a growing disparity in income distribution (Shukri 2006). In addition, 185,000 Sudanese have sought refuge in this area (WEP 2006), thus contributing to the high population.

Despite an apparent satisfactory overall food supply situation (Shukri 2006), relating to other parts of Uganda, access to food for a large number of people is limited by low purchasing power. This includes the central Uganda where food insecurity is as low as 3% (WEP 2006). Nanono's (2008) research on the Status

and Causes of Malnutrition in Kalagala Sub-County of Luweero District has also proved that vulnerability to food insecurity is a concern for it often affects 19-36% of the population in that area.

Food insecurity and its vulnerability have enormous effects, especially on women and children. If food security is not realized then there is likelihood that all suffer (Ian 2004). Indeed, 'Hunger threatens not only people's lives but also their dignity' (Pontifical Council 1996). Adequate nutrition is essential for growth, good health and physical and cognitive development, and requires a diverse diet including staple foods, vegetables, fruits, animal-source foods and fortified foods (Golden 2009, De Pee and Bloem 2009, FAO 2010a). Thus, continual food insecurity breaks down the body, leads to a loss of social sense, and ultimately death (Pontifical Council 1996). Food insecurity is not a transitory condition. It is debilitating and sometimes it deadly. It blights the lives of all who are affected and undermines national economic development across much of the developing world (FAO 1999).

Women's Empowerment and Equipment of Resources

As long as women do not have the same rights in law as men, as long as the birth of a girl does not receive the same welcome as that of a boy, Suppression of women is inconsistent with principles of ahimsa (non-violence).

Mahatma Gandhi, Harijan, on August 18, 1940 (Gita 2004)

The foregoing statement has a bearing on the researcher's pursuit. Women are still disadvantaged and efforts to address gender disparities and inequalities are critical for food security. It is contended that while food is a basic necessity, access to it is still a problem for many people in parts of the world, particularly Sub-Saharan Africa Uganda inclusive. Despite improvement, household food security has not yet been achieved. This is partly because women, who are usually at the forefront in terms of household food production, have not had access to the factors of production, especially land, finances, knowledge and skills. It is due to a concern about the consequences of protracted household food insecurity that this section seeks to determine how food security can be promoted within the framework of empowering women. The concept of the empowerment of women in our society is herein linked to their access to resources like skills and knowledge, land, and finance to sustain household food security.

Food security is a multi-dimensional development issue that needs cross-sectoral integrated approaches. Among several ways that should be employed to curb the problem of food insecurity is emancipating women. Women acting as food producers, particularly in Africa, play a pivotal role in securing food (Recka 1997; Bahiigwa 2002; FAO 2008; IFPRI 2009). Emancipating them, therefore, is key to achieving food security (Bonnard 2003; Quisumbing and Meinzen-Dick 2004). UN also maintains that the goal of eradicating food insecurity will only be achieved if the voice of the silent majority of human kind, women, is heard (UN Press Release 1998). Additionally, according to FAO, '...in many societies women tend to be less educated, less involved in the formal economy, less experienced in dealing with authorities, endowed with fewer and poorer quality productive resources, and faced with more restrictions on their mobility than men' (FAO 2010a). Consequently, FAO (2010a) identifies differences based on gender, unequal access by men and women to resources, to be one of the major reasons for food insecurity. FAO came up with three main sets of recommendations for addressing food insecurity: improving analysis and understanding; improving support for livelihoods and food security; and reforming the 'architecture' of assistance (FAO 2010b, see also Ratha, Mohapatra and Silwal 2009). But, surprisingly, their three main sets of recommendations do not prioritize the gender inequality identified. It is in this context, with specific reference with Kalagala sub-county of Luweero, that the researcher was compelled: to find out whether the emancipation women receive equips them with productive resources like land, finance, skills and knowledge to maintain household food security; to examine whether women emancipation leads to a positive attitude towards household food security; and to assess the coping mechanisms emancipated women put in place to combat household food insecurity.

Women Accessibility to Knowledge and Skills to Enhance Food Production

For food productivity, women need education, knowledge and skills. Worldwide, women continue to outnumber men among the world's illiterates by about 3:2 ratio (UN Press Release 1998, Prakash 1999). More than 130 million children globally, nearly 60% of them girls of ages six to eleven; are not attending

school. It is estimated that by 2002, two-thirds of the world's population of illiterate adults were women (IFPRI 2002). In Bangladesh, by 1999, 71% of adult females were illiterate (IFPRI 2009). The literacy rate in Uganda is male: 79.5% and female: 60.4% (FAO 2009). Yet, the investment in women's human capital is essential for food security. Such an investment, more than any other, increases women's capabilities, expands their opportunities, and empowers them to exercise their choices, greatly improving food security (Quisumbing and Meinzen-Dick 2004).

Increased accessibility of resource of knowledge and skills to women logically increases agricultural production (Quisumbing 1996). Previous studies, such as that of Quisumbing et al. (1995), Quisumbing (1996), Smith and Haddad (2005) and Smith et al. (2003) established that increasing women's education is a key ingredient for their emancipation, which invariably affects household food security. To put it differently, those who lack access to basic knowledge and skills are not likely to accept new programmes that may enhance food security within the households. The higher the educational status of women, the better their contribution to household food security. Education of girls and women is one of the most important human capital strategies of acquiring food security (Quisumbing and Meinzen-Dick 2004).

The increased education level of mothers to completion of primary school reduced the population in poverty by 33.7% in Egypt and by 23.2% in Mozambique (Datt and Joliffe 1999). In Kenya, a year of primary education provided to all women farmers was able to boost maize yields by 24% (Quisumbing 1996). With women's education, not only is there increased agricultural production, but also reduced child malnutrition by 43% (Smith and Haddad 2005) (Quisumbing and Meinzen-Dick 2004) olumakaiye and Ajayi (2006) investigated the association between educational status of women and provision of food for household members. They discovered that women with higher education are likely to provide varieties of food thereby increasing the household food security. According to Tesema (2006), at household level, higher education levels are closely linked with higher food security status.

Over-reliance on less mechanized methods of food production has effects on food security, especially in Africa. Agricultural practices in most Sub-Saharan countries are largely subsistence and cultural, with very little added value. Most farmlands are ancestral and characterized by monoculture subsistence farming; due to limited access to agriculture-related technical assistance and limited modern knowledge about advantageous soil fertility management practices. Such limitations pose a major challenge to household food security, because they lead to a loss of soil fertility, as well as environmental degradation. Additionally, over-reliance on traditional food harvesting and storage practices leads to a significant loss of food. Furthermore, the tropical climate makes foods produced in these regions prone to pests and diseases, unless the food is properly stored. Most farmers in Sub-Saharan Africa lack the capacity to add value to their produce, something that would otherwise enhance the competitiveness of their produce in international markets.

From the foregoing, it would be necessary to establish with empirical evidence, the importance of knowledge and skills towards attainment of household food security in Uganda. Poor post harvest handling technologies and inadequate storage structures, lack of knowledge and skill in that area, has been identified as key underlying causes of food insecurity in Central Uganda 2 (FAO 2010e). Illustratively, since 1992, a project entitled 'Agricultural Training in Animal Husbandry for Dairy Production' views participation as a means and an end to reduce poverty in Uganda. With the acquired resources of knowledge and skill, 690 families, including 630 women, received heifers (50% pure bred); it led to an increment in household income.

Similar results have been reported by WFPU and CEEWA-U. The former, a local chapter of WFWPI, was established in Uganda in 1992. Since then, WFPU has been concentrating on women emancipation. Believing that mothers are the pillars of the family and that knowledge and practical skills are the key to food security, WFPU has been educating and equipping women especially in life skills, developmental planning, cash crop growing and business development. On the other hand, (CEEWA-U 2006), has also registered similar improvement due to knowledge and skill imparted to women on IT and entrepreneurship.

Among the objectives of WED and ICT is to increase skills and knowledge among women entrepreneurs in ICT use and application for sustainability of project activities. In brief, emancipated females are more likely to have smaller families and healthier, more educated children as well as more food secure- due to skills and knowledge obtained (IFPRI 2009). Charlotte (2000) also noted that improving women's access to education and training opportunities enhances their human capital as an input to ensuring individual and household food security (FCND 1999). It is in this context that the researcher was to examine if the emancipation women of Kalagala sub-county receive equips them with skills and knowledge to improve household food security.

Women Empowerment and Attitude Towards Household Food Security

Attitudes toward changing roles for women have been the subject of numerous recent studies (Gidarakou 1999, Obosu-Mensah 2000, Simon 2005, and Liaghati et al 2008). Traditionally, the attitudes of rural residents have been portrayed as being more conservative than the attitudes of urban residents. But, generally, men and women have divergent perceptions of their participation in food productivity. They think differently about the level of their own participation. For some activities both agree on job specialization by sex. For example, both think that land preparation should be either men's or joint work; also that seed and water collection should be mainly women's work. However, women believe they are participating more than men think they do (Muntemba and Ruvimbo 1995).

Empowered women, especially those in the rural, have positive attitudes towards agricultural production of food. They have an 'understanding' that agriculture is an increasingly important factor in achieving food security (Abu, Samah, and D'Silva 2010). Across the world, with positive attitudes, rural women provide most of the labor for farming, from soil preparation to harvest. After the harvest, they are almost entirely responsible for operations such as storage, handling, stocking, marketing and processing (UN Press Release 1998, Prakash 1999). Women in rural areas also generally bear primary responsibility for the nutrition of their children, from gestation through weaning and throughout the critical period of growth. In principle, they are the principal food producers and preparers for the rest of the family.

Women relate positively to the various tasks of food security as part of their daily work. Their attitudes towards their changed roles, as breadwinners instead of men, enable them to manage productive resources. They have accumulated intimate knowledge of their ecosystems, developing strategies for managing change. They have amassed valuable knowledge in such areas as plant genetics, pest management, and soil conservation. For example, in Zimbabwe, according to Muntemba and Ruvimbo (1995), women farmers do not buy seed to grow basic foods: millets, sorghum, peanuts, groundnuts, and sweet potatoes. They *select* seed, looking for particular traits, such as stability, disease resistance, drought tolerance, palatability and storage potential. In some cases, however, the break from the familiar base has not led to positive adjustment and innovation, as producers attempt to follow technological practices without sufficient scientific support.

The findings of Abu, Samah, and D'Silva (2010) confirm that women have high (70%) positive attitude towards farming. Several variables, including religious affiliation, educational level and employment status, are expected to influence their attitudes towards agriculture and food security. According to a study completed by Obosu-Mensah (2000) and Ali and Anwar (2000), education greatly influences women's attitude towards farming. Appleton (1994) affirms that knowledge is essential in women's attitude towards technical innovation for food productivity. Appleton (1994) defines innovation as: 'Any change, however small, in the skills, techniques, processes, equipment, type of organization of production that enables people to cope better or take advantage of particular circumstances'. Elsewhere Appleton (1993a, 1993b, see Carr 1981) claims that technological improvements and innovations can result from improvements in skills and organizational systems; and more interestingly, from changed attitudes. Generally, studies have shown that attitudes are becoming increasingly less traditional and are influenced by socio demographic variables (Gidarakou 1999, Ali and Anwar 2000, Da Silva 2005, Guo, Robert and Jianhua 2007 and Liaghati et al 2008).

Even though previous studies have proved that youth have unfavorable attitude towards farming (Gidarakou 1999, Barlet, Labao and Meyer 2004), recently Norsida (2008) in her study found that youth, ladies inclusive, highly believe that agriculture can generate higher income for them if it is handled in the right

way. Indeed, the women have a better attitude towards agriculture generally and farming specifically because it is obvious that they are the backbone of the agriculture in the globe, particularly in developing nations. Rural women are actively involved in the process of food production, processing and marketing. It is, therefore, in this context that the researcher evoked to explore whether emancipation of women in Kalagala sub-county leads to a positive attitude towards agricultural production with the aim of achieving household food security.

ANALYSIS AND PRESENTATION OF FINDINGS

Social Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

The study first looked at the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents, which included, sex, age, marital status, number of people fed in the household, size of land for the family, size of land under cultivation, respondents education level and occupation. The socio-demographic characteristics were essential so as to know and understand the type of respondents since their views were worth noting.

The social demographic information of the respondents as revealed from the study in Table 1, 89 % of the respondents were women, who were the target population; while the rest (11%) were male. The majority of respondents (44%) ranged between 31-36 years of age, 23% were between 41-50 years, 22% in the ranges of 21-30, 8% were over 50 and only 3% were below 20 years of age. Considering the marital status of the respondents, 72% were married, 18% were single, 7% were widows and 3% were divorced. Observations and interviews revealed that though married, many women were staying alone with their children, thus making a big number of female headed households.

Table 1 also showed that 48% of the respondents were responsible for feeding at least 5-8 people in their families, 22% fed 9-12 people, 11% fed 13-16 people, 14% fed 1-4 people and only 1% fed above 17 people as dependants in their households. On the question of land ownership, the findings revealed that 30% of the respondents pointed out that they had less than an acre and 28% had 5-6 acres. Results further indicated that 20% of the respondents had between 1-2 acres, 16% had 3-4 acres and only 6% had over 7 acres of land. The interviews given to group leaders also revealed that most of the respondents had less than one acre of land and the rest was unused. Results indicated that 33% of the respondents cultivated less than an acre of land, 30% cultivated between 1-2 acres, 29% cultivated between 3-4 acres, 5% cultivated between 5-6 acres, and only 3% cultivated over 7 acres. From observations, most respondents who had less than 1 acre of land cultivated all of it. The respondents who had above 5 acres of land cultivated very little of it, leaving most of it unused.

Table 1: Demographic Information of the Respondents

<i>Gender</i>	Frequency	Percent
Female	311	89
Male	40	11
Total	351	100
<i>Age bracket</i>		
Below 20 years	12	3
21 - 30 years	77	22
31 -40 years	154	44
41-50 years	81	23
Above 51 years	27	8
Total	351	100
<i>Marital status</i>		
Single	66	18
Divorced	9	3
Widowed	24	7
Married	252	72
Total	351	100
<i>Total number of people fed daily in your household</i>		
Above 17 people	18	5
13 -16 people	38	11
9-12 people	78	22
5 - 8 people	169	48
1 - 4 people	48	14
Total	351	100
<i>The size of the land owned by the family</i>		
Less than an Acre	107	30
1-2 Acres	70	20
3-4 Acres	56	16

5-6 Acres	98	28
Over 7 acres	20	6
Total	351	100
Size of land under cultivation		
Less than an Acre	116	33
1-2 Acres	105	30
3-4 Acres	100	29
5-6 Acres	19	5
Over 7 acres	11	3
Total	351	100
Respondents Level of education		
No formal education	23	7
Primary level	206	59
Secondary level	93	26
Diploma/certificate holder	28	8
Degree/ post-degree holder	1	0
Total	351	100
Occupation for a living		
I am a casual worker	54	15
I am a salaried worker	9	3
I own a private [small] business	31	9
I am trader [big business]	10	3
I am a [small scale] farmer	247	70
Total	351	100

On the level of education of the respondents, 59% of the respondents revealed that they went up to primary level, 27% went through secondary education but never went beyond that, and 8% went beyond secondary school and obtained certificate and diploma in various fields of study. Results also showed that 7% of the respondents never obtained any formal education and that none of them had gone through degree and post degree level.

In reference to respondents' main occupation, the majority of the respondents (70%) were engaged in small scale farming, 15% indicated that they were casual workers, 9% were small business holders, 3% were salaried employees and another 3% were engaged in large scale trading.

The Concept and Nature of Food Security

As already mentioned, food security is a condition that prevails when individual members of a specific family have either material or financial access to sufficient, safe, and nutritious food stuffs to meet the dietary basic needs, at family level. The researcher sought for data on household food security in the study area and the findings are as presented in Table 2 and Figure 1:

Table 2: Meals taken by household members per day

Type and Number of meals per day	Frequency	Percent
Only one meal taken in the evening	10	3
Breakfast and Lunch only	42	12
Breakfast and Supper only	92	26
Breakfast, Lunch and Supper	191	54
Always more than three meals taken	16	5
Total	351	100

Source:Field Data 2011

In regard to the number of meals taken by the respondents, results showed that 54% of them revealed that they had three meals (breakfast, lunch and supper) a day, 26% had breakfast and supper, 12% had breakfast and lunch, 5% had more than 3 meals and only 3% had only a meal a day taken in the evening. When she interviewed the group leaders, most of the respondents, said that most of the times they could afford only two meals a day that is breakfast and supper .though some said they had only lunch and supper.

Figure 1: Meals taken by household members per day

The researcher also sought to assess the most common constrain in regards to food production. The results are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: The most common constraints in production of food for the home

Type of constraint	Frequency	Percent
No training in Agriculture	60	17
Diseases and pests during farming	130	37
Climatic changes	90	26
Lack of labour for farming	21	6
Lack of funds for farming	18	5
Lack of enough land for farming	32	9
Total	351	100

Source: Field Data (2011)

In relation to the most common constrain, results in Table 3 indicate that majority of respondents (37%) disclosed that diseases and pests of crops during farming were the common constraint, while 26% indicated climatic changes as the major constraint. Lack of agricultural training was cited by 17%, lack of enough land for farming by 9%, and lack of labor by 6%. Only 5% cited lack of funds for farming as a major constraint. From the interviews held, it was also noted that women were not the ones responsible for discussions made on the farm; for example, types of crops to grow, size of acreage to put under certain crops; and even after producing that food, their husbands were the ones who managed the harvests.

The researcher moreover wanted to find out the availability of food throughout the year and results are presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Period of the year when food was not available

Period in the year	Frequency	Percent
Jan-Feb	83	24
March-April	212	60
May-June	45	13
July- Aug	5	1
Sept-Oct	5	1
Nov-Dec	1	0
Total	351	100

Source: Field Data 2011

Majority of respondents (60%) indicated that during the months of March to April food was not available, while 24% indicated that this occurred in January and February. Another 13% indicated scarcity of food during the months of May and June. Only 1% indicated scarcity of food during the months of July August and the months of September to October. None indicated scarcity of food during the months of November to December.

On availability of food in the market, 78% of the respondents indicated that they had never missed food in the market while 22% agreed that there was a time when they go to the market and find no food. According to the interview conducted, food was available but not affordable. The group leaders who were interviewed revealed that most of the times they could get food in the market but at higher prices.

“There is always food in the market, but affording it is a problem. The prices are hiked and it only becomes easier for the rich” Said one of the respondents.

Additionally, the researcher wanted to find out the availability of some of the foods in the study area. The foods were considered under the headings of always available, sometimes available and never available. Rankings of ‘Never available’ =1, ‘Sometimes available’ =2, and ‘Always available’ =3 were used to rank the various foods by the respondents. And results are shown in table 5 below.

Table 5: Rating of availability of food

Type of food available	Mean rating
Eggs	1.72
Milk	1.72
Meat	1.62
Beans	2.25
Gnuts	2.14
Sweet potatoes	2.46
Cassava	2.36
Bananas	2.26
Maize flour	2.18
Tomatoes	2.13
Dodo	2.23
Eggplant	2.16
Nakati	2.08
Sukumawiki	1.83
Cabbage	2.01
Pawpaws	2.01
Pineapples	1.56
Oranges	1.42
Apples	1.12

Source: Field Data (2011)

Key

- 1.00-1.70 Never available
 1.80- 2.40 Sometimes available
 2.50-3.00 Always available

The mean rating of the responses as never available at were eggs at 1.72, milk at 1.72, meat a mean rate of 1.62, pineapples at 1.56, oranges at 1.42 and apples at 1.12.

The foods which were sometimes available were cassava rated at 2.36, bananas rated at 2.26, beans at 2.25, Dodo (*Amaranthus*) at 2.23, maize flour 2.18, eggplant 2.16, Nakati (*Solanum ethiopicum*) 2.08, cabbage 2.01, papaws 2.01, and Sukumawiki (Kale) 1.83. Only sweet potatoes were rated as always available at the mean rate of 2.46. The researcher also tried to find out the level of income in the household and the proportion of this used to buy food. Results are shown in table below

Table 6: Total monthly income (in Ug. shs) for respondents' households and proportion used to buy food

Total monthly income (Ug. shs)	F	%	Proportion of income used to buy food	F	%
Below 61,000/=	273	78	½	216	62
121,000/= - 61,000/=	59	17	¼	81	23
180,000/= - 120,000/=	15	4	¾	51	15
239,000/= - 179,000/=	3	1	All of it	3	1
Over 240,000/=	1	0	Total	351	100
Total	351	100			

Source: Field Data (2011)

Table 6 indicates that 78% of the respondents earned below 60,000 Ugandan shillings, 17% earned between 60,000 and 120,000, 4% between 120,000 and 180,000, 1% between 180,000 and 240,000 and none of the respondents earned over 240,000. Additionally, 62% of the respondents indicated that they used half of their monthly income in buying food, 23% used ¼ of their income, 15% used ¾ of their income while 1% used all their income on food.

Research was done on the most common diseases children in the study area suffered from. The diseases were obesity, anaemia, kwashiorkor, marasmus and rickets. Respondents were required to indicate the diseases their children suffered from most and the results are presented in Table that follows.

Table 7: Most common diseases that children of the respondents have ever suffered from

Common child Disease	Frequency	Percent
Obesity	2	1
Anaemia	18	5
Kwashiorkor	61	17
Marasmus	26	7
Rickets	8	2
None	236	67
Total	351	100

Source: Field Data (2011)

Majority of respondents (67%) indicated that their children had never suffered any of the mentioned diseases, 17% indicated that their children had suffered from kwashiorkor, 7% cited marasmus, 5% anemia, 2% rickets and only 1% indicated obesity. From the observations made by the researcher, it was also observed that most of the households had children who were either suffering from kwashiorkor, marasmus or both because most had protruding stomachs, scanty brown hair and thin legs and arms; symptoms which are indicative of those two diseases.

Conclusions and Recommendations

The majority of the respondents (89%) were women since the study was concern with women emancipation and its effects on household food security. Thus, the women felt that it is always in their domain and responsibility to provide food and that they were the target population. The majority of respondents (44%) ranged between 31-36 years of age which can be attributed to the fact that this is an active stage and were more willing to come forth and take part in the study. Considering the marital status of the respondents, 72% were married, 18% were single, 7% were widows and 3% were divorced. Observations and interviews revealed that though married, many women were staying alone with their children, thus making a big number of female headed households.

Majority of families had between 5-8 people to feed. This is true of most Ugandan households which have an average of 6 people who live with them as dependants. Most respondents owned and farmed an average of 2 acres or less. This is in agreement with Ejacor (Mukiibi J. Editor. 2000). Check in who said that most farmers in Uganda are small scale of about 2 acres or less. It was found that most of the women were farming on their husband's land and were not responsible for decisions made on the farm. Such a scenario makes farming ineffective because those who are responsible to do the actual farming are not the ones making the relevant decisions. It was also found that most respondents had only primary level education. This can render them unable to comprehend the more complicated issues of agricultural production and might adversely affect the quality and quantity of production from the farms.

The study findings are in agreement with Jules-Rossete (1992) who notes that lack of education forces women into the informal sector dominated by small enterprises, petty trading, and crafts as ways of coping with the different situations. The findings on the concept of household food security revealed that 54% of the respondents had three meals per day; although from observation, most people in the study area had two meals a day. Respondents might have recorded 3 meals a day so as not to feel embarrassed by the fact that they were not getting all the required meals. On further interviews, those who said that they had three meals a day revealed that even taking just strong tea without milk in the morning was counted a meal; although such a meal would not be balanced. This is in agreement with (FEWS NET 1997) and at 36.8% (IFPRI 2006) who stated that Uganda has a relatively low national rate of food energy deficiency, rated at 37%, yet, majority of Ugandans do not have access to sufficient food (WEP 2006). The diet is poor consisting mainly of staple foods (roots and tubers) and rarely vegetables, fruits or animal proteins.

The most common constraint that respondents faced in food production was diseases and pests during farming at 37% followed by climatic changes at 26%. Furthermore, through the interviews held, it was found out that climate change, diseases, lack of technology and small land under farming were some of the constraints faced by farmers. Jaggard et al. (2010) also pointed out that climate change also affect food production through rises in sea level that risk inundating coastal agriculture, reductions in glacier cover that might drastically change the hydrology of rivers critical for irrigating large agricultural areas, and possibly through increases in pest and disease incidence, though the latter is very hard to predict accurately.

From the study findings it was noted that Kalagala women, like all other women, faced challenges with the climate which hinders their efforts towards curbing food insecurity in their area. The changes in rainfall patterns are harder to predict, and different regions will experience both higher and lower precipitation. Extreme events in general are likely to be an increasing problem for food production, with droughts, high temperature extremes, floods and (more controversially) tropical storms all likely to increase in frequency. The study therefore revealed that as much as empowered women were working hard towards household food security, they were hindered by factors beyond their control like climatic change which they could not predict. Therefore, it remains a fact that though emancipated, women face challenges in food production which hinders household food security.

It was also found that food was not continuously available and that there were times when it was in plenty and times when it was scarce. Carbohydrates like sweet potatoes and cassava were always available, whereas proteins like beans and groundnuts and vegetables like Dodo (*Amaranthus*) and 'Nakati' (*Solanum ethiopicum*) were sometimes available. Fruits on the other hand, especially apples and oranges were generally scarce, although pawpaws were sometimes available. Normally food is scarce during planting and growing time of crops and the results agree with this concept because it was found that it was mainly scarce during the months of April to May when most of the seeds had been planted. Usually carbohydrates especially cassava are more available throughout the year because these are root crops which stay in the soil for a long time. However, in the study it was found that it was mainly sweet potatoes that were available throughout the year with cassava rated as being sometimes available. This may be because cassava takes a longer period than sweet potatoes which takes at least three months and therefore those who have the cassava might opt to sell it rendering it not to be sometimes available.

It was also found out that income for households was very low, the majority of respondents getting less than 60,000/= which is about 30 US dollars per month. Since income was very low it made possibilities of

supplementing food with purchased food items very difficult and so ushered in food insecurity. The current study findings concurs with those of Kavitha et al. (2008), who noted that with reference to income levels, a significant percentage of women in Uganda earn an annual household income of less than USD 360 where the monetary return and the need to stabilize the family financially tend to further motivate women to become entrepreneurs. This could further explain why Kalagala women entrepreneurs vis a vis women entrepreneurs in other developing economies, are driven more by necessity than opportunity. These findings are also similar to those of Reynolds et al. (2002) who suggest that entrepreneurs in low income areas are more likely to be necessity than opportunity driven.

Nutritional diseases were abundant especially for children and from observations, marasmus and kwashiorkor were very rampant in the area although most respondents indicated an absence of these nutritional diseases. This might have been due to the fact that they were ignorant of the symptoms of these diseases or they attributed these symptoms to other causes like witch craft but not malnutrition.

Based on the findings of the study, we have described the paradox that lies in the fact that the number of those threatened by food insecurity is increasing despite international pledges to “end hunger.” Although national governments acknowledge the need for food self-sufficiency, most of the women continue to be marginalized as assets, information, and technology pass into the hands of the financially and politically powerful. Male-dominated power structures fail to relate to women at a time of acclaimed acknowledgement of the latter’s contribution to agricultural, specifically food, production.

From the foregoing; it is instrumental to understand that woman empowerment is a complex involving the women, their male counterparts, and the institutions that mind people development. Women's Empowerment should be viewed from the perspectives of the underlying principles. This therefore means empowering women is to enable them participate fully in economic life across available sectors as an essential to building stronger economies both locally and internationally to achieve the global goals from MDGs to SDGs to enhance development and sustainability, and thereby improve the quality of life which extends beyond women thus the narrative of boy child in danger meets its premature death through such. The arising effects of proper women empowerment in Kalagala will see household food insecurity turn itself to prosperity.

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